

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

DELIVERABLE D6.1: COMMUNICATION STRATEGY & ACTION PLAN

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CDB	Communication Dissemination Booster
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IA	Innovation Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
SOPs	Standard Operation Procedures
TechMall	Technology Mall
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WFRM	Wildfire risk management
WG	Working group
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

The main purpose of this document is to describe the Communication Strategy & Action Plan of the Firelogue project, highlighting the different communication target audiences, the tools and methodologies utilized towards their effective involvement in the project's activities.

Firelogue will bring together 3 Innovation Actions and FirEURisk, thus creating a dialogue between new and existing solutions in the field of wildfires. This document will evolve in line with the development of the overall project work and activities in close collaboration with all work packages and Firelogue partners as well as the Innovation Actions (IAs) and FirEURisk.

In brief, within this document we defined the narrative of Firelogue, including the goal, the values and the mission of the project through:

- Outlining the objectives of the communication activities;
- Describing the target audiences and core messages;
- Specifying channels and tools to be used in promoting the project's results and outcomes.

1 Introduction - Communication Plan

1.1 What is Firelogue?

Firelogue is a European project, funded by Horizon 2020 under the Green Deal call¹, that brings together expertise from all around Europe when it comes to Wildfire Risk Management. From researchers to civil society organisations, Firelogue’s partners have the experience, knowledge, together with a forward-thinking attitude that has placed them at the front and centre of all aspects related to WFRM to contribute with solutions and knowledge exchange.

Figure 1: Firelogue partners. Source: own figure

1.2 Goal

Firelogue aims to create a dialogue and empower the WFRM community to face the current and future wildfire challenges. Firelogue is going to act as an exchange enabler of knowledge through the aggregation of experience and best practices of all stakeholders.

To achieve the aforementioned goal, a coherent communication strategy is needed. The Communication Strategy is part of Firelogue's WP6 “Dissemination and insight upscaling”, whose main objective is to ensure that Firelogue's impact project is maximized through an effective communication and dissemination campaign, supported by engagement activities.

¹ [European green deal - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/intermediary/pdf/20220301-01.pdf) (01.03.2022).

Firelogue's Communication includes an aligned strategy with the successful IAs, (DRYADS, SILVANUS, FIRE-RES) and the FirEUrisk project. Having a Common Communication Strategy, including a joint digital presence is of primary importance to reflect the same values. Working jointly with the IAs, Firelogue will target relevant audiences (such as public authorities, policy makers, WFRM associations, and others) with key messages and relevant communication channels per target audience.

1.3 Values

Firelogue's values are based on the common identity of all the partners involved in the project with a strong focus on Cooperation, Synergies, Awareness, Dialogue, Sustainability, Research and Development, Innovation and Science, under the umbrella of the *Just Transition concept*.

1.4 Mission

Our mission is to create a space and the conditions to boost communication within the WFRM community and society, as well as retain and share the knowledge and the experiences gathered alongside the showcase of innovative actions and products.

1.5 Objectives of the Communication Strategy

The objectives of the Firelogue Communication strategy are:

- To raise awareness within practitioners and civil society and beyond about the great advance and importance that Firelogue represents to be able to construct a smooth and good dialogue within wildfire sector;
- To stimulate and provoke the cooperation and synergies of the different actors in the framework of WFRM community;
- To empower the WFRM community to face the current and future wildfire challenges;
- To engage Firelogue network's target groups to provide inputs and learn from each other's best practices and expertise;
- To support and inform relevant policy makers of project activities and main outcomes that might be useful for policy purposes, and in large extent to offer more knowledge and security for the civil society;

These objectives are the Firelogue's compass to orientate its communication plan. These activities are the pillar to the sustainability of the project itself even after the end of the life project. We take care very much in consideration the Communication part to spread Firelogue's message into the general public.

1.6 Why Communication Matters: Our Challenges

Firelogue's main communication challenges are based on the immense diversity of backgrounds, experiences, goals, and target audiences of all of those involved. But these challenges are also Firelogue's strengths that will make it the repository and dialogue enhancer between all the stakeholders as well as between the stakeholders and their target audiences.

The communication plan devised for Firelogue takes into account this diversity and will be implemented based on the following methodology:

- 1) Communication Identification of:
 - a. **target audiences:** By gathering dynamic feedback from all the partners and through surveys sent to the IAs;
 - b. **key messages:** Based on the feedback given by all the partners, and by the definition of target groups, specific key messages are developed for each objective;
 - c. **communication channels:** Based on the defined target audiences, Firelogue's communication channels will be as diverse as its partners. These channels will allow for an optimal dissemination of the key messages created.
- 2) Dissemination: Dissemination in the context of Firelogue relates to the public disclosure of the results of the project, while communication is a continue promotion of the common action itself. While objectives, target audiences, core messages, channels and tools for dissemination and communication differ for obvious reasons, they might very often coincide. Firelogue's dissemination will be ongoing, dynamic, and engaging using the communication channels defined during the Identification step. More details can be found in Deliverable 6.2, Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan.
- 3) Evaluation: Firelogue will use Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in order to evaluate the success of the communication actions both online and offline.

The key aspects of Firelogue related Communication activities are detailed in sections 2-6 below. The evaluation including the KPIs are described in Section 7.

Figure 2 refers to the Stakeholder tree created during the writing of the proposal. This figure shows that Firelogue's target isn't only to affect European countries but to contribute to wildfire events internationally. Firelogue will act as "Network Facilitator" for the International Wildfire Risk Management Community networks supporting Firelogue along three main pillars:

- i) Supporting the IAs in connecting with the networks,
- ii) Managing and connecting the WFRM identified stakeholders
- iii) Involving additional WFRM stakeholders during the life-time project

Figure 2: Firelogue Ecosystem. Source: own figure

2 Target audiences and key messages

Firelogue aims to integrate the entirety of the WFRM community. However, it is important to narrow down and identify our target precisely. In particular, we identified 7 target groups, including civil society and policy makers as detailed below.

1. **Policy/ Decision Makers:** Firelogue will establish a communication platform where end-users will be able to find information on how wildfire services and data can support their line of work. The Firelogue website will provide end-users with the opportunity to be informed about activities within the IAs and to connect with service providers. Firelogue incubates fire-prevention services that are developed with and for the users.
2. **Scientific Community:** Supporting research and academic institutions within and outside the consortium by promoting their skills and capacities, exchanging knowledge on specific thematic areas (i.e. in relation to the IAs), and finally creating synergies with other actors in the value chain and with other initiatives.
3. **Civil Society:** The Firelogue website will provide easy-to-understand information on the socio-economic and environmental benefits of fire prevention services and applications in the areas covered by the IAs. The project brings together a unique team of experts with the aim to enhance the exploitation of fire prevention information services towards informed decision-making.
4. **Media:** Firelogue consists of 15 partners and will engage several stakeholders in different countries. Through national and local media the project will establish a media presence in those channels. Firelogue website will also include information about relevant and current news on WFRM that can be used by media outlets.
5. **Local and Regional Authorities:** Firelogue will share knowledge, information, and best practices that can be useful and implemented in their respective activities, directly and via already established channels by Firelogue's partners
6. **Fire and Rescue Services:** Firelogue will raise awareness to the fact that wildfire services and solutions can be a cost-effective source of a wide-variety of valuable data. Fire and Rescue Services can benefit from these innovations, making their work more efficient.
7. **Industry:** New and innovative products and solutions will be developed by the IAs that can enhance wildfires' four stages of action (i.e. prevention, preparedness, restoration and adaptation) giving the industry important feedback on the real needs that exist and that can be exploited.

Table 1 Key Messages vs Target Audiences

	KEY MESSAGES	TARGET AUDIENCES
1	A one stop repository for IAs publications, documents, and data – Firelogue Website and Communication Booster will provide documents and data that any interested stakeholder can have access to.	Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services
2	A connecting link between stakeholders and citizens – Firelogue will act as a link via social media and the website	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities
3	An informative platform for relevant and current wildfire related news – Firelogue will be an informative factor for wildfires with the help of newsletters, conferences, workshops, articles, etc. However, the content of these products will be adapted to suit the target audience.	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers Fire and Rescue Services Media
4	A "firemap" of where and when – Firelogue in cooperation with the IAs will be a firemap to the public. Those interested will be able to follow satellite maps of forest regions (created by the IAs), a mobile app will be created by an IA to inform citizens for wildfires and provide the necessary information of how to act properly.	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities Industry Media
5	A Market Place of fire solutions and applications – Firelogue will create a Market for the technologies developed by the IAs.	Policy/ Decision Makers Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities Industry

Figure 3: Firelogue Key Messages. Source: own figure

Here is a representation of the Key Messages. Each corresponds to one icon.

Figure 4: Firelogue Target Audiences. Source: own figure

Here you can find the Target Audiences and which Key Message each one matches.

Figure 5: Firelogue Keywords. Source: own figure

This figure was inspired by the contribution of our partners. The figure shows the key words partners used to describe Firelogue.

3 Brand Identity

Firelogue’s brand identity is the summary of all the previously described elements, combined into a future-oriented, all-encompassing shape that puts the WFRM community at the centre, but is always open to dialogue with the wider set of stakeholders.

“Let the dialogue begin” resumes the essence of Firelogue’s values and goals, as well as its mission. The logo, along with the visual elements that go with it, position Firelogue as the receiver, enabler, and disseminator of a constructive dialogue that starts from within and spreads beyond.

3.1 About our Logo

Firelogue's logo was created to convey, in a single and simple element, our core values, mission, vision and goals. As the most visible element of Firelogue’s communication our aim was to create a logo that was immediately recognisable and relatable.

Creating a logo is a vital part of our project’s communication efforts. To meet this need, we created guidelines which will be available under the page “Outreach” of the Firelogue website. This file is used to share the most important messaging elements of our brand with the partners. In this manual you can find information about our logos, font, colour palette and brand imagery and you will also see recommendations on how to use them.

3.2 Main pillars of Firelogue’s Brand identity:

1. Credibility - everyone should trust and believe on us;
2. Clarity - everything must be sound and clear;
3. Reliability - apply the same method to the same sample under the same conditions
4. Readability - up to the smallest size;
5. Scalability - to any size required
6. Reproducibility- without material restrictions;
7. Memorability - that impacts and does not forget. The logo conveys the image of the essence of our product.

These pillars represent the values that Firelogue has based its Brand Identity on. Firelogue will provide information and solutions based on the quality of credibility, with a big focus on the fact that the products and services of the IAs will perform their intended function adequately and after the end of the project's life and will operate in a defined environment without failure. All solutions and services of the IAs will be available in a clear framework on Firelogue's website.

Figure 6: Firelogue Branding Pillars. Source: own figure

Brand pillars show who you are. More importantly, the pillars show how you connect on a human level. A brand's visual identity must be adaptable and flexible while still maintaining its core principles. Firelogue's brand development was based with this in mind: a modern, relatable, brand that can evoke curiosity in every medium.

We have created a minimal corporate identity manual which shows the Firelogue logo, its basic use and prescribes its applications in communication materials. You can see below some basic elements; the full logo manual can be found in the annex. It is important to state that the logo manual was distributed to the Innovation Actions.

3.3 Elements of the Firelogue corporate identity manual

One of the main goals of the Communication plan is to create a set of promotional and communication materials designed specifically to appeal to the target audience. To that end several online and offline materials will be produced:

3.3.1 Online

Figure 7: Application of the Firelogue logo

The application of the Firelogue symbol and logotype is permitted in all its dimensions down to a minimum of 20 mm.

Logotype's minimum size for print and online applications. Apply only the symbol without the logotype.

Above you can find the correct use of Firelogue's logo application (spacing, height etc.)

Figure 8: Use of Motto

Let the dialogue begin

Let the dialogue begin

The motto can be used either in one line or three.

Figure 9: Colour Palette

C: 0 M: 100 Y: 100 B: 0
R: 194 G: 11 B: 25
Hexadecimal: #c20b19

C: 0 M: 0 Y: 0 B: 100
R: 0 G: 0 B: 0
Hexadecimal: #000000

The RGB colours to be used are specific.

Figure 10: Colour Version on the Recommended Backgrounds

Application of Firelogue logo on different colour backgrounds.

Figure 11: B/W Version

Application of Firelogue logo in B/W.

Figure 12: Incorrect Treatment of Logo

Wrong applications of Firelogue logo

Figure 13: Typography

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890!\$%&@#/() ? °

Ub-Helvetica - Regular

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890!\$%&@#/() ? °*

Ub-Helvetica - Italic

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890!\$%&@#/() ? °**

Ub-Helvetica - Bold

***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890!\$%&@#/() ? °***

Ub-Helvetica - Bold Italic

Correct use of fonts for text application

Figure 14: PPT Template

**Fire 4 thought for
the platform**

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534

Figure 15: e-banner

Figure 16: Application of Online Material (Facebook)

Figure 17: Application of Online Material (Twitter)

3.3.2 Offline

(Communication Materials-printed)

- **Flyer:** The main flyer will be disseminated at the events attended or organised by FireLogue. It contains a description of the main objectives and impacts of the project.
- **Folder:** Folders, containing information and handouts, will be distributed throughout the project, especially during the FireLogue events.
- **Bags:** Bags will be distributed at conferences and events and can serve to hand-over information material by FireLogue, the IAs, FirEurisk and other projects.
- **Lanyards:** Lanyards with FireLogue logo will be created for use in conferences and events.
- **Banners/Posters:** include the main information about the project and will be used at FireLogue’s outreach events.

Figure 18: Flyer

Figure 19: Folder

Figure 20: Bag

Figure 21: Lanyard

Figure 22: Poster

Figure 23: Rollup Banner

4 Internal Communication

Firelogue as knowledge Repository

The internal communication strategy intends to ensure a constant and effective exchange by sharing information between the partners and effectively communicate the knowledge generated throughout the project's activities. Therefore, the main goal of the project's internal communication is to develop appropriate communication activities and mechanisms for a smooth and effective communication exchange within the project partnership.

Given that Firelogue brings together 15 organizations from across Europe, effective internal communication can present significant challenges. To overcome these, several actions have been envisaged:

WP6 collaborates with the Project Coordinator in order to communicate and share information with all partners in a quick, convenient, and effective manner. Moreover, mailing lists have been created in order to facilitate effective internal communication.

Through **MS TEAMS** the participants will be able to inform WP6 and the consortium about meetings and events of relevance to Firelogue in which they have participated or will participate (and eventually represent the Firelogue project), as well as about their publications and their communication actions on a monthly basis. All the report forms will be available on this page so partners can report their actions.

Firelogue communication & dissemination material is available for download via MS TEAMS:

- **A general Firelogue presentation**, conveying Firelogue's main points, key messages and supporting information, that each Firelogue's partner can add content according to their **needs and purposes**;
- **The logo and visual material** for social media use is available for all the partners to download and use;
- **Templates for documents and presentations**;
- **Other communicative materials**. For example, a Christmas card was created and shared with all partners;
- **A list of communication responsibilities of each partner** was compiled to share communication and dissemination actions with communication counterparts inside the Consortium. An application like **MS TEAMS** is already used with the main goal of sharing all the necessary information effectively, quickly and easily. MS Teams will reduce email traffic with the Communicators_ and increase interaction. Our aim is also to expand the Communicator's network beyond the Consortium. Finally, our intention is to organize a series of communicators' workshops, within the framework of fire events, in order for all of us to transmit ideas and information, address issues and plan what we want from our communication. In addition, the lessons learned, best practices and achievements will be shared with the community. With this process, the group will become more aware of its actions and the things we can do to ensure that our messages get received "loud and clear".

Linkages with other Work Packages

The Communication Strategy has interdependencies with all the other WPs of the project. Therefore, in defining them, the project team strongly considered the goals, objectives and needs of the other WPs.

WP6 will work closely with **WP1** and its continuous review of WFRM activities. Based on **Task 1.2 (Knowledge Consolidation and Integration into Firelogue platform)** and in close collaboration with WP6, this WP facilitates the gathering and exchange of knowledge between stakeholders, linking formal and informal WFRM networks. It provides dedicated exchange formats to the IAs and facilitates the coordinated exchange with the wider WFRM community and particularly additional research projects such as the LC-CLA-15 and -16 activities.

Task 2.1 of WP2 (Conceptualisation of IA discussion formats) develops in close collaboration with **Task 7.3 “Stakeholder Management”** and **WP6** on Communication and Dissemination the conceptual basis for IA exchange formats, namely Digital Annual Conference, Joint Impact Assessment Workshops and Peer Review. **WP6** will work closely with **Task 2.1** on Communication and Dissemination actions such as Annual Conference, the Dialogue Workshops and Peer Review, **Task 2.2** on Knowledge Sharing and **Task 7.3** on “Stakeholder Management” actions. Liaising with the IAs and EC services such the “Results Booster” are further measures that fall within this area.

Task 6.3 “User engagement and communication booster” will support not only communication but also the exploitation of the IA results. The Task will furthermore develop a **Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)** page on the project website that organises and provides comprehensive replies to common questions related to WFRM identified through the web-interface. Finally, a dedicated **ticketing software** will be developed to coordinate and manage the dispatch of requests for information received through the interface, ensuring that requests are forwarded to the right individual in the consortium, or the IAs respectively, and addressed in a timely manner. The **Communication Support tool software** will be based on an open software solution so that makes it reusable in any possible way (Communication Support tool - knowledge base). Finally, this Task will also liaise with the **Dissemination and Exploitation Booster services** which encourage projects to come together to identify a common portfolio of results and provide them with recommendations on how best to disseminate them to end users, with an eye on exploitation opportunities. Task 6.3 will hence also **support the Innovation Actions** to submit their request for respective support services and to apply for one of the CDBs services. In collaboration with other actions, the services mentioned above will achieve a higher and more targeted impact.

In addition, and in close collaboration with Task 2.2 “Facilitation of knowledge transfer formats”, Firelogue WP6 will implement online and physical exchange formats. These may include webinar formats already up-and-running such as the #FireHomeSchool Webinar series by partner PCF, and also other initiatives addressed to a broader audience as for example art exhibition formats and movies. Finally, Firelogue will seek to promote cross-border and regional exercises, that will be crucial activities to gain information on recommendations for harmonised training and standard operating procedures.

The **TechMall** (Firelogue Task 2.3) provides a “window to the market” of technologies developed by the IAs an FirEUrisk including a short description of their Technology Readiness Level (TRL). This TechMall will be integrated into the Firelogue platform (Communication Booster) under WP6 and will closely collaborate with the Knowledge Sharing and Good Practice activities under **Task 2.2** as well as Stakeholder Management under **Task 7.3**.

Moreover, WP3 is strongly connected to WP6, as it will help in the collection of impact assessment methodologies and will disseminate the Baseline Assessment (D3.2) and the “Action Plan” and Roadmap on how to harmonise WFRM impact assessments towards 2030, including suggestions for specific criteria, parameters and datasets to facilitate this process (D3.3), which will be developed accordingly.

Finally, **WP4 Task 4.2** creates a methodology to capture the workshop results of the thematic Working Groups (WG) and also cross- WG discussions with the aim to translate them into policy recommendations, jointly with the IAs and FirEUrisk. WP6 will support this undertaking by communication the results towards its different stakeholders but to also suggest their involvement in the final drafting of recommendations.

In general, Communication, dissemination, and exploitation initiatives are strongly related to all other WPs as a horizontal activity of WP6 in the project. The most important linkages with WPs are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Linkages with other WPs

WP	Linkages
WP1 (Consolidation of IA WFRM Knowledge)	Iteration I & II of mapping and description of wildfire events, WFRM actors, measures, technologies and SOPs completed and available via Firelogue platform 1st Iteration of TechMall online.
WP2 (Stakeholder engagement and Knowledge exchange for the support dimension)	<p>Publications: Journal Articles, Book, White Paper and Roadmap published and available via the Firelogue platform.</p> <p>The WP2 is responsible for the implementation of 4 cross-IA Impact Assessment Workshops; Integration of WG dialogue results into the impact assessment; design of Key Performance Indicators and assessment of the impact of individual measures and solutions.</p> <p>WP6 will Integrate the results in the Firelogue platform and facilitate the communication of results towards different types of stakeholders.</p>
WP3 (Common impact assessment methodology of WFRM innovation actions)	<p>Support the collection of Impact Assessment methodologies.</p> <p>Communication of the harmonised approach.</p> <p>Dissemination of the baseline assessment.</p>
WP4 (Dialogue formats for the coordination dimension: WFRM integration of measures and strategies)	<p>Based on Task 4.1 and in close collaboration with Task 1.4, this WP designs workshop formats to discuss the implication of WFRM measures and approaches from different perspectives. It will create interactive digital, physical and hybrid formats including the use of online tools such as Miro to facilitate the exchange of actors while jointly identifying stakeholder objectives, potential conflicts and the joint efforts needed to integrate measures into consistent strategies.</p> <p>Task 4.2 creates a methodology to capture workshop results and document proceedings which will be promoted by WP6.</p>
WP5 (Evaluation and recommendations for cross-sectoral and multi-stakeholder WFRM)	<p>Translate findings into continuously updated multi-stakeholder WFRM recommendations on future aspects to be addressed in Europe.</p> <p>Integration into the Firelogue platform (WP6) and communication to Firelogue stakeholders.</p>
WP7 (Stakeholder Management, CSA Coordination and Consortium Management)	<p>This stakeholder management is linked with clustering as described in section 1.3.2.3 as well as with all Firelogue communication and dissemination activities and particularly the design of the Communication Booster via the digital platform.</p> <p>Foster dissemination activities and exchange formats among the networks of the International Wildfire Risk Management Community and with Firelogue.</p>

5 External Communication

Firelogue as a Dialogue Enhancer

External communication refers to the communication between Firelogue partners and the community of interest identified in the target audience section above. The main focus in our External Communication is on the Innovation Actions (see Section 6 below). Firelogue communication must consider the following points when any message is communicated or disseminated:

- Clear, concise and direct messages;
- Use a formal and accurate vocabulary and language;
- Appropriate tone to the target audience and goals e.g., motivational, instructional, etc.;
- Message with content according to the needs and interests of the target audience.

The brand identity mentioned above gives Firelogue a recognisable and coherent image. This establishes the basic principles to be applied to the entire range of communication products. Combined with other communication tools and materials Firelogue aims both at reaching as many target audiences as possible and achieving the highest impact.

5.1 Communication Channels and materials

Firelogue's communication tools will be developed and tailored based on the different needs of the specific audiences targeted by the project. The tools that are going to be used will be utilized in the course of the project towards the engagement of different target groups. More specifically these tools are the following: Website, e-news, leaflet/ brochures/ posters, social media, press releases and media contacts.

5.2 Website

The Firelogue website (D6.3) will be used throughout the project as a main distribution platform for general project information, relevant project news, project results, FAQs, detailed description of the Innovation Actions, a calendar of events and meetings and will serve as a communication platform within the consortium and with external interested parties. Regular updates of the website aim at sustaining the interest of the existing audience, presenting attractive content for potential visitors, expanding stakeholder's catalogue as well as providing new services that will be developed, such as the TechMall. [Firelogue's website](#) is designed with accessibility and user experience in mind, allowing visitors / users to navigate across the various web pages easily and quickly. The website will feed all the other communication channels referenced within this chapter.

Also, the website will provide access to all (public) Firelogue Deliverables, Roadmaps, joint publications and other documents of interest and will be GDPR compliant. It will also contain all communication outputs, from press releases to promotional materials and presentations, as well as the Firelogue Communication Platform to support the exchange of information among project participants and among external interested stakeholders. Finally, a dedicated ticketing software will be developed to coordinate and manage the dispatch of requests for information received through the interface, ensuring that requests are forwarded to the right individual in the consortium or the IAs respectively and addressed in a timely manner. All Deliverables and their content are to be made accessible via the website.

Figure 24: Firelogue.eu Homepage

5.3 Communication Booster

Firelogue, in its effort to connect services and stakeholders, will create a platform for communication and interfaces. This platform will be an area of information, innovative solutions, and services given by the IAs. This allows to provide “one face to the European Union” and being able to distribute the IA results in a coordinated manner as well as to redirect any WFRM related requests to the IAs and additional WFRM stakeholders. This stakeholder management is linked with clustering as well as with all Firelogue communication and dissemination activities and particularly the design of the Communication Booster via the Firelogue digital platform. In addition, the Communication Booster will provide a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) section on WFRM. In close collaboration with the Firelogue partners, IAs, and EU stakeholders such as DRMKC, sustainable options to maintain the Firelogue platform, in the long run, are being sought and discussions are ongoing on existing platforms such as the Lessons on Fire platform run by our partner PCF.

5.4 Social media (engagement and monitoring)

Over and above other traditional media (website, etc.), social media constitutes a powerful channel for the real-time, continuous engagement of the various stakeholders following the progress of the project. Moreover, through establishing a presence on the most relevant social media platforms the project will pursue the establishment of a “dialogue” with the related target groups, and the general public. Thus, based on the key messages communicated by the project, threads related to specific project activities will be launched.

Firelogue has already set accounts in the following social media platforms: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram. Firelogue’s social media channels will amplify, with custom messages for each platform, the projects activities and developments. All channels will be monitored regularly, so strategy can be updated during the project. All partners are expected to suggest interesting accounts to follow and to send interesting links or articles to the communication manager. This monitoring can bring relevant information to the project and create opportunities of engagement from all. Also, several tools available on the platforms will be used to engage in dialogue with our followers and others (e.g. polls)

Social networks aim to increase users’ interest and promote engagement. The objectives of these social media channels are to raise awareness of Firelogue and to encourage users to interact with the consortium. Social media of the Innovation Actions are already interconnected with those of Firelogue to expand the project’s impact to various WFRM communities.

During the first 3 months of the project, 18 tweets were posted and the project account in twitter attracted 88 followers (Firelogue Tweets earned 22.1K impressions over this period), 12 news were posted on Facebook and attracted 143 followers, 9 posts in Instagram with 62 Followers, where in LinkedIn Firelogue LinkedIn page attracted 51 followers so far.

Figure 25: Twitter Insights (first 3 months)

Figure 26: Facebook page

Figure 27: Instagram page

Figure 28: Twitter page

Figure 29: LinkedIn page

5.5 Technology Market Place / TechMall

A dedicated Technology Market Place or TechMall will be developed, offering a “window to the market” of the technologies mapped and assessed. The TechMall will be an online marketplace for technologies and services being developed with regards to WFRM. Its goal is to provide support to IAs, stakeholders and other interested parties through a single marketplace where everyone can explore and compare different services and solutions. Offered services will be grouped to different WFRM phases (Prevention, Preparedness, Response, Recovery) including contact details of the relevant research group, company, or any other entity. The TechMall will be integrated with the Firelogue platform.

5.6 European Commission communication channels

There are a series of free of charge communication channels provided by the European Commission that are going to be used within Firelogue’s lifetime in order to disseminate the results. These are the following:

- Research and Innovation Success Stories;
- Horizon Dashboard;
- Horizon Magazine;
- Horizon Impact Award.

Firelogue will facilitate the Innovation Actions to use the abovementioned channels in order for their results to be disseminated in the best possible way.

5.7 Communication Material

Communication material is a very important tool for interaction with the various target audiences. Flyers, posters, rollup banners, lanyards and other printed material will be used as well as online such as graphics, website banners, infographics etc. Therefore, Firelogue will use online graphic material to define the basics of the project: what Firelogue is about, goals, information about beneficiaries and partners, countries involved, stakeholders, etc. Banners for both social media and website will be created as well as other graphic materials for social media will be used to feed social media. All the above are mentioned and visualized at “Brand Identity” section (section 3).

5.8 Partners

Firelogue’s 15 partners will be one of the resources for Communication and Dissemination through their strong networking and own communication channels. For example, TIEMS communication channels will be available for providing news and results from the Firelogue project, so as TIEMS Newsletter (quarterly), updates from TIEMS President (once a month), webinars (monthly), annual conferences, (once a year), etc. Listing all partners with their own resources for Firelogue Communication and dissemination, will strengthen our Communication Action Plan. All the other partners will add to the communication of the project through their network and communication channels.

6 Communication with IAs

The Innovation Actions, [DRYADS](#), [SILVANUS](#), [FIRE-RES](#), and [FirEUrisk](#) aim at producing plans and arrangements on improved research products, technical solutions and services regarding the three phases of Wild Fire Risk Management: Prevention & preparedness, Detection & Response, and Restoration & Adaptation, according to European Green Deal goals.

Firelogue will coordinate and support those IAs by integrating their findings across stakeholder groups and fire management phases.

Given that each one of the IAs and FirEUrisk have their own specific objectives and will entail the involvement of different communities, it is imperative that appropriate methodologies are developed to ensure optimal attraction with the various stakeholders and efficient communication of project outcomes to them. Additionally, WP6 will maintain an overall coordination of communication and dissemination activities across the IAs. In any case communication with IAs will be made regularly via bilateral online meetings with the people responsible for communication in each IA and FirEUrisk.

Firelogue's Communication Team (NOA and EDGE) initiated these meetings in February 2022 (8 February with Silvanus and 10 February with DRYADS and FIRE-RES). Within these meetings a common ground for cooperation was found and it was agreed that there will be a regular follow-up every two months.

In that context, the following cross-cutting considerations for the implementation of IAs specific communication activities will be considered.

6.1 Social media

The social media of IAs and Firelogue will be interconnected, and cross-postings will be made on a regular basis. Firelogue will support and communicate IAs on the social media channels where IAs do not have a social media presence (e.g., Instagram).

6.2 Common visual identity and messages

Taking into consideration that the Innovation Actions already have drafted their own branding identity (e.g., Logos) we will proceed with common messages and *mottos* that can be used throughout the communication of all projects. Thus the "Let the dialogue begin" motto of Firelogue is proposed to be used as a hashtag, thus helping us to support the development of a European WFRM community and help in the notion that all the results are perceived by everyone as integrated.

Moreover, a common presentation will be drafted and disseminated to the innovation actions including information and the key messages of IAs and Firelogue.

6.3 Common Activities

- IAs will organise and participate in common events, workshops, exhibitions. For example, Firelogue is currently supporting the organisation of a *Clustering Event* organised by the EC, facilitating the exchange across the IAs, FirEUrisk and additional wildfire risk management projects.
- Common campaigns on fire-related international days will be deployed. Firelogue and IAs together will promote and embrace core WFRM values in an international day such as May 4th – International Firefighters Day.

6.4 IAs/FirEurisk – Firelogue Internal Communication

The communication teams of IAs/FirEurisk and Firelogue will e-meet regularly on a monthly basis in order to exchange updates regarding forthcoming activities like conferences, updates on the website etc. This has already been agreed upon between the respective teams during initial bilateral meetings that took place virtually throughout January/February 2022.

6.5 Recognition and visibility rules - Disclaimer

All communication items and publications must include recognition of financing by the European Union and include the following text: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036534. The EU cannot under any circumstances be held responsible for the content of the communication items prepared by project partners.

6.6 Overall

A major challenge for Firelogue is to build a community of existing and new fire-related projects. Firelogue also aims to link the results of already established projects so as to enhance their impact and solutions.

Firelogue is already in contact with other projects and EU Initiatives such as FirEurisk, EFFIS, Lessons on Fire and SAFERS aiming to continue the dialogue about new ideas and to make use of their technologies in order to achieve better results based on Firelogue's KPIs.

7 Evaluation

The main objective of WP6 Dissemination and insight upscaling, is to ensure that the input of the Firelogue project will be maximised through an effective campaign of communication and dissemination activities.

The communication activities relate to the stakeholder engagement and the dissemination activities. Thus, the tools developed as part of the communication strategy will be leveraged in a holistic approach. Appropriate indicators to assess the impact of dissemination and communication include: **a)** Visits/views and engagement of website and social media using tools such as “Google Analytics” and Social Bakers (for social media) **b)** Followers/connections, social media outreach, a popular indicator due to their widespread adoption; **c)** Number of scientific publications, academic citations, views in platforms like ResearchGate; **d)** Participation/attendance in workshops, conferences through Firelogue’s presentations or demonstrations;

The detailed analysis of the impact of the individual activities of the project will be carried out during the lifetime of the project as its activities develop. As an input to that end the following table summarises potential indicators.

Table 3 Evaluation KPIs (as described in GA)

Increase awareness of scientific results	Scientific publications (cross-IA)	Paper: 5 Conference proceedings: 1 Book: 1
	Presentations at International Conferences	20
	Articles in media and magazines	10
	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	7
Target a wide range of audience using tailored communication tools	Number of visits to the project website	15.000 unique visitors
	Followers on social networks	1000
	Communication material produced	1 brochure, 200 copies; Digital: 100 e-banners, e-news etc.)
	Youtube Video Channel views	>1000

8 Next steps

The elements of the strategic communication plan presented herein will be updated and enhanced as the activities of the project progress.

Reports on communication and dissemination activities, as well as more detailed presentation of the proceedings of conferences and workshops will be provided regularly. In the meantime, all project partners will be asked to provide information to the WP6 on their activities to monitor and potentially boost communication output. Finally, as the project is implemented, according to how the cooperation with the Innovation Actions goes at a practical level, we will provide even more targeted actions that will be included in our strategy.

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